

Lived Experiences of Badjao Street Dwellers in Metro Manila

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Abstract. The Badjao, who have traditionally been recognized for their sailors and coastal lifestyles in their hometown, are known as the "Sea Gypsies" of the southern Philippines with a distinct culture that is strongly linked to the sea. The purpose of this qualitative study was to investigate and comprehend what are the lived experiences of the Badjao Street Dwellers in asking for alms because it addresses the lived experiences received by the Badjao, a marginalized community that is sometimes disregarded in social policy discussion. The researcher used a Qualitative research method, conducting in-depth semi-structured interviews to collect data from six (6) Badjao Street Dwellers who were asking for alms in the cities of Metro Manila. The purposive Sampling Technique was used to select the participants. To analyze and organize the patterns of their responses, the researchers used Thematic Analysis which reveals eight (8) emergent themes from their experiences, two (2) from perceived benefits and coping mechanisms, and four under-life realizations. The results of the study reveal that Badjao Street Dwellers have various strategies to sustain eating daily. By asking for alms, they have accumulated their essential needs and gathered money. However, the participant encountered numerous challenges, such as marginalization, financial and property issues, and hardships in life with no progression. To cope up, they tried to be passive and thrive in life and realized to aim for a good future for their children, a new perspective, and still come home.

Keywords: *Experiences, Perceived Benefits, Badjao, Asking Alms, Street Dwellers, Coping Mechanisms*

Introduction

The Badjao, or Badjau, also known as “Sea Gypsies,” is a semi-nomadic ethnic group from Mindanao, belonging to the Sama people. They mainly live in regions like Tawi-Tawi, Sulu, Basilan, and Zamboanga del Sur in the Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM), as well as in parts of Southeast Asia, especially Malaysia. The Badjao are skilled divers and navigators who traditionally made a living through fishing, yet over time, they have sought better opportunities in urban areas, including Metro Manila. Most now reside along Roxas Boulevard and the side streets of Baclaran in Pasay City, where they survive by begging for food and alms (Soriano, n.d.). In different places, the Badjao name can be spelled in various ways, reflecting the diversity of their communities (Lucero, et al., 2020).

A report from the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) highlighted that some Badjao street dwellers earn 5,000 pesos a day from begging, which underscores the fact that the Badjao lack the skills to engage in land-based work and are solely dependent on begging. As a result, children are often found begging in public places, running alongside jeepneys, writing

solicitation letters, or singing for alms to supplement their parents' income. This exposes them to the risk of accidents and illness (Dator, et al., 2018). The Badjao are culturally very thrifty and frugal, as they believe no one will be there when they need money in an emergency. To avoid such situations, they prefer to spend all their available money on immediate family needs and earn money themselves (Malong & Salvation, 2018). Homelessness also presents significant challenges, such as exposure to extreme weather conditions, lack of privacy, and social exclusion, which make survival on the streets much harder and further complicate their lives (Mones, et al., 2024).

In summary of the research above, further research about the Badjao explored their original community, natural living, factors for taking the risk to go places for opportunities, and financial behavior. Other researchers focus on the experiences of Badjao street children as their participants, yielding a result of prioritizing earning money over attending school. Furthermore, the research locale of these researches is the provinces of the Philippines. However, there is insufficient exploration of the experiences of adult Badjao street dwellers found in NCR, specifically asking for alms in the

cities of Metro Manila. This research aims to explore the experiences of Badjaos through perceived benefits, challenges, coping mechanisms, and their life realization.

Badjao Street Dweller

Badjao Street Dwellers are members of the Badjao community, a boat-dwelling people with natural and traditional sea-based lifestyles. The semi-nomadic group was believed originally inhabited the Southeast Asia archipelago, particularly in Borneo, Malaysia, and Eastern Indonesia, and some migrated to the Philippines in the Mindanao islands, particularly scattered in Tawi-Tawi, Basilan, Sulu, and other parts of Zamboanga City (Ethnic Groups of the Philippines, 2023).

From their original homes, many of them left their homes and migrated to cities like Manila due to various circumstances and challenges, hoping to find vast opportunities in urban areas. There are numerous challenges that Badjao people encounter in their homes, including life-threatening armed conflicts, drastic economic issues, cultural stigma, and misconceptions, lack of support systems, and urban nomadism, etc. which result in begging on the streets by themselves or with their family (Valle, 2015).

From the study conducted by Dator et al., (2018) children from the Badjao community typically spend their time with other kids begging for money, delivering letters of solicitation in white folders and envelopes, and singing in return for cash or any other sum.

Badjao street dwellers are scattered not only in Manila. In other parts of the Philippines such as Kalibo, Aklan Mayor William Lachica expressed his concerns about the increasing number of Badjao - young men and mothers with young children asking for food and cash in the capital city. In addition, Badjaos street dwellers in the city have turned to begging as a means of livelihood since they lack proper employment or sources of income (Zabal, 2017). According to the findings of Mabanglo et al., (2020) study, Badjao street dwellers' lifestyle exploited newborns or children to make them appear more pathetic and miserable. Furthermore, it's observable that every Christmas, a mass of Badjao people is scattered and wanders in crowded areas such as Metro Manila, particularly along Claro M. Recto in Quiapo (Necio, 2014).

Badjao Experiences as Street Dwellers

Badjao's main concern is feeding their family. Living near the sea, their primary source of food is fishing, however, changing from water to land they are not used to such a way of living, leading them to resort to asking for alms (Dator et al., 2018)

Daug et al. (2013) noted that begging has become the primary source of livelihood for Badjao families. They start their day early, with Badjao mothers heading to the streets, often bringing their young daughters and infant children to evoke sympathy from passersby. The boys typically carry makeshift drums made from plastic to use as musical instruments. Meanwhile, Badjao men generally stay behind in the community in Tambacan, as their status as men makes it harder for them to persuade others that they need assistance. Meanwhile, in Bukidnon, the Samal Badjaos routine began in the morning or the afternoon. Women and children accompany them to crowded areas. It's a must to have more family members to beg as they can collect more money (Anino, 2020).

On the other hand, begging is easier said than done. Badjao people experience numerous challenges and difficulties while begging. The study of Perena and Hapin

(2023), shows that the adult Badjao occasionally encountered accidents, especially with those disabilities. They also revealed that they sometimes faced harsh words from others. These unfavorable conditions, both directly and indirectly, impacted their activities. They regard these issues as the most distressing circumstances they experience. For instance, they are often treated harshly because of their untidy appearance (Mabanglo et al., 2020) called dirty people, and experience prejudice (Salvaña and Taynan (2017).

In regards to this Baffoe (2013), mentioned that societal barriers make it hard for people with disabilities to be included and have access to opportunities. In the same way, the Badjao experience exclusion and are not accepted in communities.

Additionally, the Badjao teens face a significant language barrier when interacting with others, which hampers their ability to communicate effectively. This challenge is particularly evident when they ask for alms, as their inability to express their needs often leads to misunderstandings or feelings of being ignored (Geyrozaga & Dungog-Cuizon, 2021). Because of this, they find it difficult to connect with people, which makes them feel isolated and like they're not

being heard. This communication problem is a big challenge that affects their experience and the benefits they get from asking for alms.

Another major challenge the Badjao community has faced is that they were exploited due to tough life. In 2021, the Zamboanga City government was alarmed by the mass departure of Badjao in Manila. According to the report of the Inter-Agency Council Against Trafficking (IACAT), they are victims of trafficking and were forced to be mendicants and laborers and end up begging on the streets of Manila and other cities (Pareño, 2021). It was discovered that some “individuals” used them to turn into street beggars in Kalibo (Zabal, 2017).

These challenges are what Badjao encounters almost every day in their life and it is possible that the Badjao street dwellers encounter the same treatment more harshly because they are not in their livelihood and making a life in the city.

Perceived Benefits as Street Dwellers

Begging is widely used in various parts of the world and performed by individuals who are incapable of owning a property or living on the street, with limited

access to services, and have no educational attainment or possessions in hand. It is an all-in-person request to provide little support, like money, food, or gifts, for their living, especially for their family. Among all the support mentioned, they often prefer coins or cash so they can spend it according to their needs. People are intrigued about the amount they have gathered (Reinhard, 2021). After a report from Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) chief Erwin Tulfo (2022), it became known to the public that Badjao street dwellers could earn as much as 5,000 pesos in a single day. In addition to this, according to a study by Abelgas (2018), every week they typically earn between 500 to 2,000 Philippine pesos (PHP).

For instance, the study by Guerrero et al. (2022) mentioned that Badjaos often struggle to eat regularly, usually having only two meals a day. To have daily meals, children spend their days attempting to make ends meet through begging.

Street begging has changed from being an act of desperation into a matter of survival (Stones, 2013). Over time, it has become one of the most powerful thrusts against poverty and hence a major contribution to the effort for the survival of

society's less fortunate members (Bukoye, 2015).

Coping Mechanisms of Badjao Street Dwellers

Abelgas (2018) highlights that Badjao people have gone through numerous difficulties and challenges, nevertheless, their ability to adapt allows them to support their families financially and deal with changes in the economy. It shows the importance of their strong sense of community and in-group socialization, which provides a crucial support system, offering a sense of belonging and emotional support. Despite experiencing social outcasts and prejudice, the Badjao exhibit remarkable resilience, finding ways to navigate these challenges and maintain their sense of identity and worth. For instance, considering that Badjao street dwellers constantly experience rejection or people who refuse to give them alms, they just proceed and let it go. This shows their non-confrontational nature and strong values of respect (O'Callaghan, 2018). Diamante (2019) also emphasizes that Badjao people can manage to stay positive and joyful even in tough situations. Badjao demonstrates a remarkable ability to cope with adversity through a combination of faith, adaptability, strong community ties, resilience, and

shared experiences. These coping mechanisms are essential for their survival and well-being in the face of significant challenges.

Methodology

Participants

The researchers had six (6) participants for this study who were selected under pre-determined criteria. The participants of this research were Badjao street dwellers ages eighteen (18) and above, and there would be six (6) participants, male or female. They must be street dwellers roaming the streets within Metro Manila and have been asking for alms. The demographic profile of the participants includes pseudonyms, age, gender, years of asking alms, Badjao tribe name, and place of birth.

Sampling

In research investigations, purposive sampling is employed to choose a certain subset of participants or units for examination. When a researcher wishes to choose a sample that is typical of the traits they are interested in investigating and has a clear notion of those features, this technique is acceptable. In qualitative research, this kind of sampling is often used since it

enables the researcher to concentrate on particular areas of interest and collect comprehensive data on the participants. Purposive sampling will be used by the researcher to accurately pick respondents who demonstrate the characteristics according to the given criteria set by the researchers:

The Sama Bajau tribe showcases their ability to preserve cultural traditions and maintain a strong sense of collective identity (Moreno, 2023) therefore it will help the researcher to identify Badjao participants; who must be wearing an ethnic-patterned sleeve or long shirts, with or without a head wrap, because they will be identified by these clothing that is different from the non Badjao beggars that are usually just wearing untidy and torn clothes.

Research Instrument Used

The researchers employed an in-depth, semi-structured face-to-face interview as the primary data collection method. The interview consisted of open-ended questions, allowing participants to elaborate on their responses freely. The self-made questionnaires created by the researchers were validated by three experts or validators to ensure the validity of the items before use. The questionnaires were revised

according to the validators' suggestions and comments.

During the interview, the researchers took detailed notes to document the information audio-recorded with the consent of the participants, ensuring proper documentation and accuracy of the data collected.

Data Gathering

The researcher employed a qualitative research design, utilizing narrative approaches and in-depth interviews to collect data. As Creswell (2012) explains, qualitative research aims to explore and understand the meanings individuals or groups attach to social or human issues. This method is particularly suited to examining the experiences, perceived benefits, coping strategies of Badjao street dwellers, and life realization. Thematic analysis was used to identify patterns and themes within the data, providing a deeper understanding of the participants' experiences. Semi-structured in-depth interviews are used to obtain detailed, first-hand accounts from the Badjao regarding their experiences and challenges they encounter with asking for alms, the benefits they perceive, their strategies for coping with these challenges, and life realization.

Data Gathering

The Overall Thematic Map shows all the emerging themes and their corresponding clusters that organize the commonality of the responses from the participants. This study has four (4) focuses based on the statement of the problem: **Experiences, Perceived Benefits, Coping Mechanisms, and Life Realization**. The Lived Experiences has eight (8) emerging themes: Strategies, Sustenance, Social Discrimination, Financial Insecurity, Temporary accommodation, Economic Hardship, Relative Hardship, and Lack of Advancement.

Strategies with Daily Routine, Purposeful Roaming, Leaving to Avoid Unkind People, and Accepting with Gratitude as clustered themes. **Sustenance** with Getting Through the Day and Resource Availability as clustered themes. In **Social Discrimination**, there are two (2) clustered

themes: Bullied by Other People and Social Exclusion. **Financial Insecurity** with Financial Problem. **Temporary Accommodation** has a Shelter. **Economic Hardship** with Life Contrast. **Relative Hardship** with Living Standards and Lack of Social Advancement with Unchanged as clustered themes.

Perceived Benefits, also has two (2) emerging themes: Survival Necessities and Urban Opportunity. **Survival Necessities** has one (1) clustered, which is Basic Need and **Urban Opportunity** has Profit.

Coping Mechanisms has two (2) emerging themes with one (1) clustered theme each. **Passivity** is Accepting the Situation and being **Determined to Thrive** with Perseverance.

In **Life Realization**, has four (4) emergent themes: Headed Back, Ambition, Strength in Adversity, and a New Perspective on Tagalogs. The clustered themes of **Headed Back** were Returning for the Holidays and Planned to Comeback. **Ambition** Has Children's Future. **Strength in Adversity** has Endurance and **New Perspective to Tagalogs** with Urban Generosity.

Results

This research aims to explore the

experiences of Badjao street dwellers by asking alms through their perceived benefits, the challenges they encounter, their coping mechanisms, and life realization of the Badjao from all their daily living.

The findings reveal that asking for alms is the primary means by which they meet basic needs, such as food and shelter. The study also reveals that each participant receives between 200 to 400 pesos per day from alms, and many are renting homes, with daily rental costs ranging from 10 to 20 pesos per person, excluding bills and other expenses. The average person per household is 3 – 4 persons, making it a cost of 30-100 pesos per day.

In addition, it has been highlighting the prevalent issue of education among the Badjao, with many unable to read or write, knowing only their names but not their correct spellings. This lack of education significantly limits their opportunities, leaving them reliant on asking for alms to meet their daily needs. While some participants are aware of the duration of their stay in urban areas, others remain uncertain, which underscores the transient and unstable nature of their lives. Exploring the experiences that they encountered on the streets. The strategies that they impose and their ways of finding resources also how

they face social discrimination and exclusion due to their distinct appearance and cultural background

Despite the challenges their acceptance of the situation reflects their inherent kindness and resilience, as highlighted in this study. This acceptance does not mean that they are surrendering in life but it demonstrates their determination to persevere despite what comes after them.

Their strategies for coping reveal adaptability and resourcefulness, essential traits that allow them to manage their challenges and strive for survival in an unfamiliar urban environment these experiences fuel aspirations for a brighter future, especially for their children, while others dream of returning to their homeland Migration to urban areas offers mixed perspectives: for some, it represents an opportunity to provide for their families. These realizations underscore both their hope for change and the enduring significance of their cultural and personal

This study ultimately reveals the complexities of the Badjao's urban experiences, shedding light on their survival strategies, aspirations, and the harsh realities they face. It calls for greater societal awareness and increased support for marginalized communities like the Badjao,

to improve their lives and foster long-term change.

Discussion

In light of the study's findings, the future researchers recommend that Future researcher should select other indigenous people, who were asking alms in urban areas, as this study focused on Badjao Street Dwellers. Furthermore, future researchers should explore within or beyond Metro Manila. Since this study focused on adult Badjao Street Dwellers, the researchers recommend to explore the children street dwellers and the challenges they faced.

Based on the experiences of Badjao street dwellers, the researchers recommend calling the attention of the community and the government to offer educational support for the Badjaos' personal development. Furthermore, they suggest that teachers, aspiring teachers, and college volunteers who would like to teach children to read and write should get involved. In terms of the challenges they encountered in urban areas, this study recommends conducting an awareness campaign about their situation through different platforms, including social media, news, and public sharing.

For the perceived benefits, the researchers recommend that non-

governmental organizations or businesses share their expertise and expand through training programs to help the Badjao people gain knowledge and skills, enabling them to work in long-term revenue-generating ventures without resorting to asking for alms.

Regarding the coping mechanisms, the adaptability and resourcefulness they exhibit from asking alms in urban areas, this study recommends that the government, advocates, and non-government organizations collaborate with the Badjao community to restore the beauty of their homeland, improve their livelihood, preserve their culture, and showcase these coping mechanisms to support their community as one of the indigenous peoples of the Philippines.

For life realization, since they are one of the indigenous peoples of the Philippines who seek better opportunities in urban areas, the researchers suggest encouraging the government, advocates, and the Badjao community to form a plan to gather the Badjao people and help them return to their homeland by covering their transportation and expenses. Furthermore, while the above recommendations are in progress, it is suggested that passersby or every individual give at least a small amount

of money, clothes, food, or anything that can be given out of kindness.

The final recommendation of this study is dedicated to researchers and future scholars who wish to continue understanding the Badjao. They should conduct further studies on the Badjao, whether in urban or rural areas, and explore other ways to communicate with them to allow the Badjao to express themselves. Furthermore, it is important to avoid making promises merely to obtain information from them.

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